

Transcriptomic identification of potential antioxidative enzyme regulators of the gametophytic-to-embryogenic switch in barley microspores

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Scope Statement

Our manuscript investigates microspore embryogenesis (ME) as a model of plant cell totipotency, focusing on the redox-based regulation of embryogenic reprogramming. By combining transcriptomic profiling with functional categorization of antioxidant and thiol-redox systems, we reveal genotype-specific redox dynamics underlying cellular fate transition. The study provides novel insights into oxidative signaling and redox homeostasis during stress-induced cell reprogramming, which fits directly within the scope of *Frontiers in Plant Science*—**Plant Cell Biology** specialty section.

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest

Credit Author Statement

Agnieszka Springer: Formal Analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Anna Nowicka:** Formal Analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Ewa Dubas:** Formal Analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Iwona Anna Żur:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Writing – original draft. **Monika Krzewska:** Formal Analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Zbyněk Milec:** Data curation, Formal Analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Przemysław Kopeć:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing.

Keywords

Antioxidant Defense, *Hordeum vulgare*, microspore embryogenesis, Redoxhomeostasis, RNA-Seq

Abstract

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Microspore embryogenesis (ME) relies on the cellular reprogramming of the default gametophytic developmental pathway, which normally directs microspores toward pollen formation, into an embryogenic pathway that leads to the development of embryo-like structures (ELS) and, subsequently, haploid or doubled haploid (DH) plants. To test how redox control underpins this switch, we have carried out an extended in silico analysis of previously published RNA-seq data from two barley cultivars differing in ME competence (Igri, responsive; Golden Promise, recalcitrant) across four early induction stages (0–III). A curated set of 472 antioxidant/redox genes—core detoxification enzymes, the ASC–GSH cycle, TRX/GRX/PRX systems and GSTs—was examined. The analysis revealed that the expression of antioxidative defense genes is dynamically modulated during ME induction, underscoring the importance of redox homeostasis in successful microspore reprogramming. Both cultivars shared a late (stages II–III) program with increased SODs, selected CAT/GPX genes, rising MDHARs, deployment of specific TRX/GRX/PRX members and broad GSTs upregulation. Divergence emerged during progression: Igri showed a pronounced stage-III rise of GRs and targeted TRX/GRX/PRX transcripts, together with stronger activation of multiple GSTs. When considered alongside diverse experimental data, these stage-restricted, cultivar-biased signatures support a hypothetical model in which strengthened ASC–GSH recycling and thiol-redox hubs sustain H₂O₂ signaling while limiting oxidative damage. Targeting MDHARs, GRs, selected TRX/GRX/PRX genes, and GST subsets could improve ME efficiency and accelerate the integration of DH technology into modern crop breeding programs.

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No Generative AI was used in the preparation of this manuscript.

In review

Research article

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17 **Keywords:** Antioxidant defense, *Hordeum vulgare*; Microspore embryogenesis; Redox
18 homeostasis; RNA-seq

19 Abstract

20 Microspore embryogenesis (ME) relies on the cellular reprogramming of the default
21 gametophytic developmental pathway, which normally directs microspores toward pollen
22 formation, into an embryogenic pathway that leads to the development of embryo-like
23 structures (ELS) and, subsequently, haploid or doubled haploid (DH) plants. To test how redox
24 control underpins this switch, we have carried out an extended *in silico* analysis of previously
25 published RNA-seq data from two barley cultivars differing in ME competence (Igr1,
26 responsive; Golden Promise, recalcitrant) across four early induction stages (0–III). A curated
27 set of 472 antioxidant/redox genes—core detoxification enzymes, the ASC–GSH cycle,
28 *TRX/GRX/PRX* systems and *GSTs*—was examined. The analysis revealed that the expression
29 of antioxidative defense genes is dynamically modulated during ME induction, underscoring
30 the importance of redox homeostasis in successful microspore reprogramming. Both cultivars
31 shared a late (stages II–III) program with increased *SODs*, selected *CAT/GPX* genes, rising
32 *MDHARs*, deployment of specific *TRX/GRX/PRX* members and broad *GSTs* upregulation.
33 Divergence emerged during progression: Igr1 showed a pronounced stage-III rise of *GRs* and
34 targeted *TRX/GRX/PRX* transcripts, together with stronger activation of multiple *GSTs*. When
35 considered alongside diverse experimental data, these stage-restricted, cultivar-biased
36 signatures support a hypothetical model in which strengthened ASC–GSH recycling and thiol-
37 redox hubs sustain H₂O₂ signaling while limiting oxidative damage. Targeting *MDHARs*, *GRs*,
38 selected *TRX/GRX/PRX* genes, and *GST* subsets could improve ME efficiency and accelerate
39 the integration of DH technology into modern crop breeding programs.
40
41

42 1. Introduction

43 Every living cell operates as a dynamic network of biochemical reactions governed by the
44 cellular redox state. This balance—maintained through the production and removal of reactive
45 oxygen, nitrogen, and sulfur species (ROS, RNS, and RSS)—is essential for homeostasis and
46 underpins virtually all life processes. In plants, redox signals shape growth and development
47 by modulating photosynthesis, respiration, and hormone signaling, as well as the activities of
48 transcription factors and stress-related enzymes. Because plants are constantly exposed to
49 environmental stress, rapid and accurate redox signalling is critical for survival. Redox cues
50 have also been proposed as triggers of cellular reprogramming, including the shift from
51 gametophytic to embryogenic development.

52 Our earlier studies revealed a central role for ROS in the induction of microspore
53 reprogramming; whereby immature pollen grains are redirected towards embryogenic
54 development (Žur et al., 2014a; 2021a). The resulting ELSs have the ability to regenerate into
55 haploid and DH plants, highly valuable for basic research and breeding purposes. Microspores
56 also represent an attractive target for genetic engineering, including genome editing, because
57 modifications introduced into haploid cells can be stably fixed by chromosome doubling.
58 However, the efficiency of ME is strongly genotype-dependent and often varies even between
59 closely related genotypes (Krzewska et al., 2012; Žur et al., 2014a). Trial-and-error approaches
60 to improve effectiveness of ME are therefore laborious, highlighting the need to better
61 understand the underlying molecular mechanisms.

62 Advances in RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) have enabled detailed exploration of
63 transcriptional networks regulating developmental reprogramming. Earlier studies provided
64 insights into the transcriptomic changes associated with ME induction in barley (Bélanger et
65 al., 2018; 2020). Building on this, our recent work compared two cultivars that differ strongly
66 in embryogenic potential, providing a detailed map of the gene networks that orchestrate the
67 shift in cellular machinery during ME induction (Nowicka et al., 2024). Based on our previous
68 work in triticale (Žur et al., 2014a), we postulated a role for ROS in ME induction, a hypothesis
69 supported by growing evidence. Tight control of redox homeostasis therefore appears to be a
70 prerequisite for efficient microspore reprogramming. It is mediated by antioxidant and redox
71 systems that regulate transfer of electrons from donor molecules to target proteins. Within this
72 framework, antioxidant defense represents a key regulatory layer that scavenges reactive
73 molecules and reduces oxidized substrates to protect microspores, while ROS themselves
74 function as signaling molecules involved in growth, development, and stress adaptation.
75 Recently published data highlight the complexity of the interactions among ROS,
76 transcriptional and epigenetic regulators, plant hormones, metabolites, and suggest the potential
77 mechanisms underlying ROS-mediated effects (Auverlot et al., 2024; Karpinska and Foyer,
78 2024; Lin et al., 2025).

79 Core antioxidant defenses include families of SUPEROXIDE DISMUTASES (SODs),
80 CATALASES (CATs), and GLUTATHIONE PEROXIDASES (GPXs), which detoxify
81 superoxide anion ($O_2^{\cdot-}$) and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) (Fig.1A) (Mittler, 2002). The electrons
82 required for ROS reduction are supplied by metal ions, which serve as essential cofactors for
83 enzymes such as SODs and CATs. In the case of peroxidases, which require electron donors,
84 these electrons can be provided by REDUCED GLUTATHIONE (GSH), ASCORBATE (ASC)
85 or THIOREDOXINS (TRXs), all of which also participate directly in redox reactions.
86 Additional protection is provided by the ascorbate–glutathione cycle (ASC–GSH), where
87 enzymes including MONODEHYDROASCORBATE REDUCTASE (MDHAR),
88 DEHYDROASCORBATE REDUCTASE (DHAR), GLUTATHIONE REDUCTASE (GR),
89 and ASCORBATE PEROXIDASE (APX) recycle oxidized forms of ASC (dehydroascorbic
90 acid, DHA) and glutathione (glutathione disulfide, GSSG) (Foyer and Noctor, 2011).
91 Glutathione also protects proteins against irreversible oxidation through S-glutathionylation,
92 catalysed by GLUTATHIONE S-TRANSFERASES (GSTs). Many GSTs display also

93 peroxidase activity (Noctor et al., 2024 and references therein). Other important electron
94 transmitters include GLUTAREDOXINS (GRXs), PEROXIREDOXINS (PRXs) and TRXs
95 which catalyze reversible disulfide bond formation and protect central metabolic pathways
96 (Sevilla et al., 2023). Notably, the barley genome harbors multi-member gene families for every
97 antioxidant class (Fig. 1B) (Monat et al., 2019).

98 Here, we profile the transcriptional antioxidant network underpinning microspore ME
99 in barley by an extended analysis of previously published RNA-seq data from microspores and
100 microspore-derived multicellular structures sampled across four early ME stages in two
101 cultivars with contrasting embryogenic competence (Igri, responsive; Golden Promise,
102 recalcitrant (Nowicka et al., 2024). We delineate antioxidant pathways, identify stage-specific
103 markers of microspore reprogramming, and nominate candidate regulators whose expression
104 distinguish the superior ME efficiency of Igri from Golden Promise. Consistent with this, we
105 observe clear cultivar-dependent differences in antioxidant defense gene expression that likely
106 contribute to divergent ME responsiveness and may tip the balance between successful
107 reprogramming and stress-induced cell death. However, these conclusions rely on
108 transcriptomic evidence, targeted functional assays will be required to determine whether
109 reduced antioxidant activity is a primary driver of microspore mortality or instead reflects
110 downstream consequences of broader metabolic and physiological reconfiguration during ME.

111 2. Materials and methods

112 *Plant material, ME-induction stages, and RNA-seq sampling*

113 This study builds on previously published RNA-seq data (Nowicka et al., 2024) from two barley
114 (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) cultivars: Igri (winter type; HOR 10596; ME-responsive) and Golden
115 Promise (spring type; HOR 16645; ME-recalcitrant). Detailed procedures for plant cultivation,
116 ME induction, microspore isolation, and data processing are provided in Nowicka et al., (2024).
117 Four stages of ME-induction were analysed (Fig. 1C):

118 Stage 0: Microspores isolated from freshly harvested tillers.

119 Stage I: Microspores isolated from anthers pre-treated with 0.4 M mannitol for 48 h at 21 °C.

120 Stages II–III: Microspores isolated from anthers cultured in KBP medium (Kumlehn et al.,
121 2006) for 24 h (stage II) or 48 h (stage III) following the same mannitol pre-treatment.

122 Because Golden Promise is recalcitrant to ME induction, biochemical stimulation was
123 provided by co-culture with immature pistils (+p) of wheat cultivar Bobwhite (Lippmann et al.,
124 2015). Longitudinally bisected pistils (three halves per ml KBP medium) were added to isolated
125 Golden Promise microspores, and stage II–III RNA-seq samples were collected after co-culture.
126 Igri did not undergo co-culture. ME-induction efficiency and sample purity were assessed
127 microscopically prior to RNA-seq (Daghma et al., 2014). Samples for RNA-seq were collected
128 using a mannitol/maltose density-gradient method. The gradient was applied once for stage 0
129 and twice for stages I–III; stage III fractions were additionally sieve-filtered.

130 Bicellular pollen grains produced by asymmetric division were used as a gametophytic
131 control. Pollen was isolated from freshly harvested tillers: cells were first enriched by a
132 mannitol/maltose density gradient and then individually picked using a glass micropipette
133 mounted on a micromanipulator under an inverted microscope, coupled to a microinjector for
134 precise aspiration. Pollen RNA-seq data are unpublished (Kopeć P., Nowicka A., Žur I. et al.).

135 *RNA extraction, sequencing, and differential expression analysis*

136 In brief, RNA-seq was performed with four biological replicates per ME induction stage and
137 cultivar (32 samples in total) and three biological replicates per cultivar for bicellular pollen (6
138 samples). Total RNA was extracted using the NucleoSpin RNA Plant Kit (740949.50;
139 Macherey-Nagel, Düren, Germany). Samples with RNA integrity values (RIN) > 6.0 were used

143 to prepare poly(A)-selected mRNA libraries (NEBNext Ultra™ RNA Library Prep Kit for
144 Illumina). Libraries were sequenced as 150-bp paired-end reads on an Illumina NovaSeq
145 platform (Genewiz). Raw reads were adapter-trimmed using Trim Galore (v0.4.1) and aligned
146 to the *H. vulgare* cultivar Morex reference genome v2 (Monat et al., 2019) using HISAT2
147 (v2.1.0). Gene-level read counts were obtained with Subread/featureCounts (v1.5.2) using the
148 corresponding genome annotation. Differential expression analysis was performed on raw
149 count data using DESeq2 (v1.24.0) in R (v3.6.3) with the Wald test under a negative binomial
150 model. *P*-values were adjusted for multiple testing using the Benjamini–Hochberg procedure,
151 and genes with FDR < 0.05 were considered differentially expressed. Transcript abundance was
152 reported as FPKM, and log₂ fold changes (log₂FC) were calculated by DESeq2.

153 The RNA-seq dataset is publicly available in the NCBI Gene Expression Omnibus
154 (GSE233486).

155

156 *Antioxidant gene selection and classification*

157 To investigate redox-associated transcriptional responses during ME induction, we have
158 completed the RNA-seq dataset with a targeted set of antioxidant and redox-related genes.
159 Candidate functions were curated manually from biochemical pathway knowledge and primary
160 literature (Mittler, 2002; Foyer and Noctor, 2011; Sevilla et al., 2023). In total, 472 genes (Fig.
161 1B) were curated and assigned to four functional categories:

162 i) core antioxidant genes: *SUPEROXIDE DISMUTASES (SODs)*, *CATALASES (CATs)*,
163 *GLUTATHIONE PEROXIDASES (GPXs)*;

164 ii) ASC–GSH cycle genes: *ASCORBATE PEROXIDASES (APXs)*,
165 *MONODEHYDROASCORBATE REDUCTASES (MDHARs)*, *DEHYDROASCORBATE*
166 *REDUCTASES (DHARs)* and *GLUTATHIONE REDUCTASE (GRs)*;

167 iii) redox-regulated thiol genes: *THIOREDOXINS (TRXs)*, *THIOREDOXIN REDUCTASE*
168 *(TRXR)*, *GLUTAREDOXINS (GRXs)*, *PEROXIREDOXINS (PRXs)*;

169 iv) genes involved in S-glutathionylation: *GLUTATHIONE S-TRANSFERASES (GSTs)*.

170 Candidate genes were initially retrieved from the *H. vulgare* Morex v2 annotation
171 (Monat et al., 2019) using keyword- and function-based searches. When gene families were
172 incompletely annotated or ambiguous, orthologous *Arabidopsis thaliana* protein sequences
173 were used as queries for manual homology searches in EnsemblPlants to identify the
174 corresponding barley genes.

175

176 *Marker gene criteria and cross-study validation*

177 Stage-specific markers were genes that, at a given induction stage, met all of the following
178 criteria: (i) FPKM > 10 in both cultivars; (ii) no significant cultivar effect at that stage (FDR-
179 adjusted *P* > 0.05); (iii) log₂FC > 2 relative to the subsequent stages; and (iv) absent or very
180 low expression in the gametophytic control (bicellular pollen, P). Cultivar-specific markers
181 were genes that, at a given stage, met: (i) FPKM > 5; (ii) a significant difference between
182 cultivars (FDR-adjusted *P* < 0.05); (iii) log₂FC > 2 relative to the second cultivar at the same
183 stage; and (iv) absent or very low expression in P. Genes that did not meet these thresholds but
184 showed directionally consistent patterns are reported as trend-level candidates for stage or
185 cultivar specificity.

186 For cross-study validation, thiol-related and *GST* genes reported for the ME-responsive
187 cultivar Gobernadora (Bélanger et al., 2018), originally annotated against the Morex v1
188 (Mascher et al., 2017) reference genome, were mapped to Morex v2 identifiers using reciprocal
189 BLASTP searches using EnsemblPlants database.

190

191 *Data analysis and visualization*

192 Gene filtering, selection, and summarization were performed in R (v4.2.2) using custom scripts.
193 Heatmaps were generated with Heatmapper (<http://heatmapper.ca/expression/>). Matrix bubble
194 charts and additional visualizations were produced using ggplot2.

195

196 3. Results

197

198 *Cytological composition across ME-induction stages*

199 Using the published dataset of Nowicka et al., (2024), we assessed oxidative-stress-related
200 transcriptomic responses across four ME-induction stages in two barley cultivars, Igri
201 (responsive) and Golden Promise (recalcitrant): stage 0 (untreated), stage I (48 h in 0.4 M
202 mannitol at 21 °C), and stages II–III (24 h and 48 h after transfer to KBP, respectively). Each
203 stage comprised mixed cell populations with cultivar-specific composition (Fig. 1C; Fig. S1).
204 At stage 0, Igri was enriched for uninucleate microspores (73%) with fewer bicellular structures
205 after symmetric division (17%). Golden Promise contained fewer uninucleates (14%) and more
206 bicellulars (21%) whereas a high proportion of microspores remained unidentified. Stage I
207 showed comparable reprogramming ($\approx 30\%$ symmetric divisions), but uninucleates remained
208 more frequent in Igri (68%) than in Golden Promise (22%). Across stages II–III, Golden
209 Promise maintained $\approx 30\%$ bicellular structures, while multicellular structures—arising from
210 continued symmetric divisions—increased from 3% at stage II to 18% at stage III. In Igri,
211 bicellulars remained $\approx 40\%$ across stages II–III, with multicellular structures at 12% in stage II
212 and 6% in stage III. These differences were more pronounced in cultures lacking the stimulatory
213 effect of co-cultured pistils from the highly embryogenic wheat cultivar Bobwhite (–p; Fig. 1C;
214 Fig. S1). This staged cytology provides the framework for the antioxidant/redox transcriptomic
215 analyses that follow.

216

217 *Core antioxidant enzymes were reprogrammed in a stage- and cultivar-dependent manner*

218 We first profiled genes encoding the core antioxidant enzymes that constitute the primary
219 defense against ROS — *SODs*, *CATs* and *GPXs* (Fig.2, Fig. S2). Of 21 annotated *SOD* genes,
220 15 were transcriptionally active (FPKM > 0) in at least one induction stage, together with five
221 of nine *CATs* and all five *GPXs* (Fig. S2A). *SODs* spanned a wide expression range: in Golden
222 Promise, most transcripts were moderate (10–100 FPKM) with few highly expressed (>100
223 FPKM), whereas in Igri expression was more evenly split between low (1–10 FPKM) and
224 moderate levels. *CATs* were generally weakly expressed in both cultivars, while *GPXs* were
225 consistently stronger, predominantly at moderate–high levels (Fig. S2B). Most expressed *SODs*
226 belonged to *Cu/Zn-SOD* orthogroups (*Arabidopsis CSD1/2/3*), with fewer chloroplastic *Fe-*
227 *SODs* and a single mitochondrial *MnSOD*. Two *CATs* aligned with *CAT2* and several *GPXs*
228 with *GPX1/6* (Supplementary Dataset 1).

229 Family-level averages revealed distinct trends (Fig. 2A, Fig. S2C). Mean *SOD*
230 expression ranged from ~ 40 FPKM (Igri, stage II) to ~ 60 FPKM (Golden Promise, stage I),
231 with maxima at stage 0 in Golden Promise and stage III in Igri; bicellular pollen (P;
232 gametophytic control) showed *SOD* levels comparable to induction stages. *CATs* averaged 12–
233 28 FPKM and peaked at stage III in both cultivars. *GPXs* exceeded *SODs* and *CATs* overall,
234 tended to be higher in Golden Promise, and peaked at stage III (~ 180 FPKM). In contrast to
235 induction stages, *CAT* and *GPX* transcripts were low in mature pollen.

236 Gene-level profiles highlighted discrete regulatory modes (Fig. 2A,B). Among *SODs*,
237 some transcripts were induced early (stages 0–I; e.g. *MnSOD* HORVU.MOREX.r2.2HG0173140.1;
238 *Cu/Zn-SOD* HORVU.MOREX.r2.2HG0154740.1),
239 whereas others rose later (stages I–III; e.g. *Cu/Zn-SODs* HORVU.MOREX.r2.4HG0329510.1
240 and HORVU.MOREX.r2.6HG0513460.1—the latter strongly upregulated in both cultivars at
241 stages II–III with FPKM > 10 but not detected in mature pollen, supporting its candidacy as an

242 ME-stage marker). Additional cultivar specificity was evident: *Cu/Zn-SOD*
243 HORVU.MOREX.r2.7HG0573050.1 was moderate at stages 0–II in both cultivars but became
244 Igri-specific at stage III, whereas HORVU.MOREX.r2.3HG0190910.1 was confined to Igri.

245 Three *CATs* showed clear stage specificity: HORVU.MOREX.r2.1HG0067700.1 at
246 stage 0 (uninucleate microspores), HORVU.MOREX.r2.2HG0109480.1 at stage I (osmotic
247 treatment), and HORVU.MOREX.r2.4HG0341470.1 at stage III, with higher expression in
248 Golden Promise. Another *CAT* (HORVU.MOREX.r2.7HG0623480.1) increased progressively
249 across Stages II–III in both cultivars and served as an II–III marker. All *CATs* were very low in
250 mature pollen (Fig. 2A,B).

251 *GPXs* also exhibited stage- and cultivar-dependent regulation:
252 HORVU.MOREX.r2.4HG0304790.1 peaked at stages I and III, and
253 HORVU.MOREX.r2.2HG0156400.1 marked Golden Promise at stage III. As with *CATs*, *GPX*
254 transcripts were low in mature pollen (Fig. 2A,B).

255 Collectively, core antioxidant genes show dynamic regulation during ME, with stage-
256 and cultivar-specific patterns that distinguish the responsive Igri from the recalcitrant Golden
257 Promise.

258
259 *ASC–GSH cycle genes showed late MDHAR rise and stronger GR induction in responsive*
260 *cultivar*

261 We next analyzed *APX*, *MDHAR*, and *GR* families (Fig.3, Fig. S3). A distinct *DHAR* gene
262 family is not annotated in the barley Morex v2 genome; homology-based searches indicated
263 that *DHAR*-like functions are represented by GST-annotated genes (Supplementary Dataset 1).
264 Most genes were expressed (*APX*: 4/5; *MDHAR*: 5/7; *GR*: 2/2; 14 total; Fig. S3A), mapping to
265 orthogroups containing the corresponding Arabidopsis genes (Supplementary Dataset 1).

266 At the family level, *APX* genes exhibited the highest mean expression among all
267 antioxidant gene families, maintaining consistently high transcript abundance across induction
268 stages and in pollen in both cultivars (≈ 300 – 500 mean FPKM). Notably, a single *APX* transcript
269 (HORVU.MOREX.r2.2HG0088330.1) displayed very high and stable expression across all
270 ME stages and in pollen, reaching ≈ 1000 FPKM (Fig. 3A,B Fig. S3B). In contrast, *MDHARs*
271 increased progressively from stage 0 to stage III, particularly in Igri (up to ~ 77 FPKM), with
272 pollen lower than induction stages. *GRs* were expressed at moderate levels (~ 60 FPKM) across
273 ME stages and in pollen, except for a marked rise in Igri at stage III (~ 115 FPKM).

274 Gene-specific patterns reinforced these trends (Fig. 3A,B). Within *APX*,
275 HORVU.MOREX.r2.4HG0320930.1 was high in Igri at stage 0 and re-emerged at stage III,
276 showing stage-III specificity in both cultivars. Several *MDHARs*
277 (HORVU.MOREX.r2.6HG0503910.1, HORVU.MOREX.r2.7HG0581330.1,
278 HORVU.MOREX.r2.7HG0571990.1) showed progressive induction marking stages II–III,
279 whereas HORVU.MOREX.r2.6HG0503900.1 peaked at stage I in both cultivars. Among *GRs*,
280 HORVU.MOREX.r2.6HG0521730.1 emerged as a stage III-specific marker of Igri. In mature
281 pollen, *APXs* expression was high in one or both cultivars, whereas *MDHARs* and *GRs* were
282 low.

283 In summary, *APX* transcripts are abundant but largely stage-stable, *MDHARs* rise with
284 ME progression, and *GR* showed an Igri-biased stage-III induction.

285
286 *Thiol-redox regulators showed late activation with responsive cultivar enrichment*

287 We examined also the transcriptional activity of thiol–redox regulatory families (Fig. 4, Fig.
288 S4). Of 143 annotated genes, most were expressed in at least one stage: 57/63 *TRXs*, 37/56
289 *GRXs*, all 6 *TRXR*s and all 8 *PRX*s (Fig. S4A). *TRX* and *GRX* transcripts generally accumulated
290 at low-to-moderate levels, with few highly expressed members; *TRXR* and *PRX* showed similar
291 distributions (Fig. S4B).

292 At the family level, mean expression was relatively stable across stages 0–III and in
293 pollen, with only minor cultivar differences (Fig. 4A, Fig.S4C). *TRXR* was notably invariant:
294 all six members showed no clear induction with ME or genotype effects (Supplementary
295 Dataset1).

296 In contrast, several *TRXs* and *GRXs* were selectively mobilized at later stages (II–III),
297 particularly in Igri. Representative trajectories illustrated these contrasts (Fig. 4A,B). For
298 example, *TRXs* HORVU.MOREX.r2.1HG0023970.1, HORVU.MOREX.r2.4HG0315890.1,
299 and HORVU.MOREX.r2.2HG0091330.1 exhibited biphasic dynamics: high at stage 0,
300 decreased at stages I–II, then re-induced at stage III—Igri-specific for
301 HORVU.MOREX.r2.1HG0023970.1, shared by both cultivars for the other two. Strong
302 cultivar biases were evident: HORVU.MOREX.r2.7HG0534000.1 was consistently higher in
303 Golden Promise, whereas HORVU.MOREX.r2.2HG0174890.1 was higher in Igri across
304 stages. Marker-like behavior included Igri-specific induction at stages II–III
305 (HORVU.MOREX.r2.2HG0093810.1) and stage-III-restricted increases
306 (HORVU.MOREX.r2.5HG0432930.1, HORVU.MOREX.r2.7HG0560380.1). Among *GRXs*,
307 HORVU.MOREX.r2.2HG0125570.1 acted as a stage-III marker in both cultivars,
308 HORVU.MOREX.r2.7HG0552610.1 was enriched in Golden Promise at stage III, and
309 HORVU.MOREX.r2.3HG0230900.1 was Igri-stage III marker. Several transcripts
310 (HORVU.MOREX.r2.6HG0496700.1, HORVU.MOREX.r2.2HG0095970.1,
311 HORVU.MOREX.r2.1HG0072330.1) accumulated progressively across induction. Within
312 *PRXs*, HORVU.MOREX.r2.6HG0476250.1 was stage-I specific in both cultivars, whereas
313 HORVU.MOREX.r2.3HG0231680.1 showed clear Igri specificity at stage III.

314 To validate these patterns, a cross-study comparison was performed with the ME-
315 responsive cultivar Gobernadora, in which three *TRX* and two *GRX* genes were reported as
316 upregulated at day 5 of culture (Bélangier et al., 2018). The expression profiles of these
317 candidates were therefore examined in the Igri and Golden Promise datasets. Two *TRXs* showed
318 Igri stage III-specific accumulation, whereas the third was induced in both cultivars across
319 stages I–III; similarly, both *GRXs* displayed increased expression in both cultivars across stages
320 I–III (Fig. 4A, Supplementary Dataset1).

321 Notably, a subset of *TRX*, *GRX* and *PRX* genes was not ME-responsive but was strongly
322 expressed in mature pollen, indicating developmental rather than reprogramming regulation
323 (Fig. S4D, E).

324 Hence, although family-level expression appears stable, distinct *TRX/GRX/PRX*
325 members are selectively deployed in a stage- and cultivar-dependent manner, with late (II–III)
326 induction particularly prominent in Igri.

327 *Enhanced GST activation at stage III of ME in the responsive barley cultivar*

328 To assess the role of GST during ME induction, we profiled the expression of 280 annotated
329 *GST* genes (Fig. 5, Fig. S5). Exactly half of these genes (140/280) were transcriptionally active
330 (FPKM > 0) in at least one developmental stage in either cultivar (Fig.S5A). The expressed
331 *GST* genes are distributed across various classes, with a particularly strong representation of
332 the theta class (*GSTT3*, $n = 41$, Supplementary Dataset 1). Most transcripts accumulated at very
333 low to low levels (0–10 FPKM), with relatively few reaching moderate (10–100 FPKM) or high
334 (≥ 100 FPKM) abundance. Notably, the responsive cultivar Igri contained more strongly
335 expressed *GSTs* at stage III than Golden Promise (Fig. S5B).

336 Mean *GST* expression increased progressively from stage 0 to stage III in both cultivars,
337 peaking in Igri at stage III (~40 FPKM). Pollen (P) showed low *GST* expression, comparable
338 to stage 0 (Fig. 5A, Fig. S5C).

339 Closer inspection revealed diverse expression trajectories (Fig. 5A,B). Several
340 transcripts were preferentially induced in Golden Promise at stage I (e.g.
341

342 HORVU.MOREX.r2.7HG0529160.1, HORVU.MOREX.r2.3HG0267220.1) or at stages II–III
343 (e.g. HORVU.MOREX.r2.6HG0520240.1). HORVU.MOREX.r2.1HG0013750.1 was the
344 most highly expressed *GST* overall, with strong accumulation at stages II and III in both
345 cultivars. Additional common stage markers included genes specifically induced at stage III
346 (e.g. HORVU.MOREX.r2.7HG0619090.1, HORVU.MOREX.r2.5HG0383770.1). A
347 substantial subset was enriched in Igri at stages II–III, with maxima at stage III: some
348 maintained high expression across both stages (e.g. HORVU.MOREX.r2.7HG0551820.1,
349 HORVU.MOREX.r2.3HG0260240.1), whereas others showed a stepwise rise from moderate
350 (stage II) to strong (stage III) levels (e.g. HORVU.MOREX.r2.1HG0040480.1,
351 HORVU.MOREX.r2.1HG0016790.1, HORVU.MOREX.r2.1HG0040620.1,
352 HORVU.MOREX.r2.1HG0016800.1). A final group acted as Igri-specific stage-III markers
353 (e.g. HORVU.MOREX.r2.2HG0178470.1).

354 Similarly, cross-study comparison with the ME-responsive cultivar Gobernadora
355 supported the stage specificity observed here (Bélanger et al., 2018). Seven *GST*s reported as
356 upregulated at days 0–2 of culture were examined in the present dataset and were found to be
357 associated primarily with early induction: three were upregulated at stage I in both cultivars but
358 accumulated more strongly in Golden Promise, whereas four showed elevated expression
359 across stages 0–II; in all cases, expression declined at stage III. In contrast, of 19 *GST*s reported
360 as upregulated at day 5, thirteen displayed clear Igri stage III-enrichment, including seven genes
361 with strict marker-like behavior. This concordance was taken as independent validation of the
362 dataset and supported the association of late *GST* activation with responsive genotypes (Fig.
363 5A, Fig. S5D, Supplementary Dataset1).

364 Together, these results indicate that *GST* activity intensifies during the transition to
365 embryogenesis, with a pronounced stage-III induction in the responsive cultivar Igri.
366

367 4. Discussion

368 Studies in triticale and barley have shown that ME induction is accompanied by the
369 accumulation of ROS, which act as key determinants of microspore fate—promoting
370 embryogenic reprogramming at moderate levels but triggering cell death when excessive (Žur
371 et al., 2008; 2009; 2014a; 2019; 2021a; 2021b). To identify antioxidant components that sustain
372 a pro-embryogenic redox balance, we conducted an *in silico* analysis of genes encoding major
373 antioxidant and redox enzymes in two barley cultivars with contrasting embryogenic potential.
374 Despite well-documented differences in ME responsiveness (Kumlehn et al., 2006; Žur et al.,
375 2021a), cytological analysis showed that both cultivars initiated microspore reprogramming
376 with comparable efficiency at stage I and displayed a broadly similar profile of antioxidant gene
377 expression at this early step. Divergence became apparent 24 h after transfer to induction
378 medium. It was most pronounced at 48 h, when the number of differentially expressed genes
379 peaked. These observations support a model in which an initial, shared activation of antioxidant
380 genes enables survival and entry into reprogramming, whereas cultivar-specific transcriptional
381 programs emerging later contribute to differential embryogenic competence.
382

383 *Elements of antioxidative defense identified in barley microspores and activated during ME* 384 *induction*

385 Our survey revealed a broad antioxidant repertoire in barley microspores: 35 core
386 antioxidant genes, 14 ASC–GSH cycle genes, 143 *TRX/GRX/PRX* genes, and a large *GST*
387 family (280 members). A similarly large set of 330 *TaGST*s was reported in wheat (Wang et
388 al., 2019). Approximately 80% of these genes were transcriptionally active during ME
389 induction. Significant expression changes were detected for nearly 80% of core antioxidant and

390 *TRX/GRX* genes, ~90% of *ASC*–*GSH* genes, and ~70% of *GST*s—evidence of extensive redox
391 rewiring during induction.

392
393 *The dual role of core antioxidative enzymes in microspore protection and differentiation*

394 Among core enzymes, *SODs* emerged as prominent candidates. Most annotated *SODs*
395 corresponded to *Arabidopsis* Cu/Zn isoforms localized to the cytosol, chloroplasts, or
396 peroxisome. These isoforms were also the most abundant in anthers of triticale subjected to
397 ME-inducing cold pre-treatment (Žur et al. 2014a). They are known to function in development
398 and respond strongly to temperature, drought, and salinity (Gill and Tuteja, 2010; Wang et al.,
399 2016; Li et al., 2017). Genotype-biased differences were clearest at stage III, where several
400 *SOD* transcripts (e.g. HORVU.MOREX.r2.7HG0573050.1) accumulated more strongly in the
401 responsive cultivar Igri. Similarly, increased accumulation of *SOD* transcripts was observed in
402 *Brassica napus* microspores redirected towards ME (Rueda-Varela et al., 2025).
403 Functionally, *SODs* catalyze the dismutation of $O_2^{\cdot-}$ to H_2O_2 , thereby limiting the formation of
404 highly reactive $\cdot OH$ via the Haber–Weiss reaction (Mittler, 2002). Being less reactive, H_2O_2
405 acts as a signaling molecule that modulates gene expression and enzyme activity through
406 cysteine oxidation-based redox regulation (Souza, 2025). Our previous work supports a role for
407 H_2O_2 as a trigger for ME as excessive H_2O_2 elimination improved microspore survival but
408 reduced reprogramming efficiency (Žur et al., 2014a; 2021a). It suggests that maintaining a
409 signaling-competent H_2O_2 pool is essential for successful ME induction. However, subsequent
410 studies in triticale and barley demonstrated that both $O_2^{\cdot-}$ and H_2O_2 accumulate in the
411 microspore cytoplasm after ME-inducing treatment (Žur et al. 2021b). Notably, enhanced
412 generation of $O_2^{\cdot-}$ was detected in proximity to the nuclei, pointing to its potential role in early
413 signaling events. This interpretation is consistent with recent insights summarized by Karpinska
414 and Foyer (2024), who highlight a previously underappreciated function of superoxide in
415 compartment-specific signaling within the plant cell nucleus.

416 Consistently, *CATs* showed stage-specific expression—distinct isoforms predominating
417 at different phases—whereas many *GPXs* (with higher affinity for H_2O_2 and frequently
418 implicated in signaling) were induced by mannitol and further upregulated at 48 h of *in vitro*
419 culture. Higher *CAT* and *GPX* transcript abundance in Golden Promise (e.g. *CAT*
420 HORVU.MOREX.r2.4HG0341470.1; *GPX* HORVU.MOREX.r2.2HG0156400.1) may reflect
421 over-scavenging that dampens H_2O_2 signaling required for the developmental switch, consistent
422 with the negative non-linear relationship between *CAT* activity and ME efficiency reported in
423 triticale (Žur et al., 2014a).

424
425 *Functional divergence of ascorbate and glutathione during ME induction*

426 Low-molecular-weight antioxidants *ASC* and *GSH* are abundant and widely distributed
427 in plant cells. They directly detoxify ROS, protecting cell components from oxidative damages
428 and help maintain the cellular redox environment required for effective metabolism and
429 development. Their oxidized forms (MDHA, DHA, GSSG) are efficiently recycled in the *ASC*–
430 *GSH* cycle due to concerted action of reducing enzymes (MDHAR, DHAR and GR; Foyer and
431 Noctor, 2011). Two observations stood out. First, several *MDHAR* transcripts increased
432 progressively during induction—either similarly in both cultivars or with a stronger response
433 in Igri (e.g. HORVU.MOREX.r2.6HG0503910.1 and HORVU.MOREX.r2.7HG0581330.1)—
434 consistent with sustained *ASC* recycling during reprogramming. Second, one *GR*
435 (HORVU.MOREX.r2.6HG0521730.1) showed a cultivar-biased induction at stage III,
436 consistent with prior evidence that elevated *GR* activity is associated with microspore
437 competence for ME (Žur et al., 2021b). In contrast, *APX* transcripts were highly abundant but
438 largely stage stable in both cultivars, suggesting a constitutive role in maintaining basal H_2O_2

439 detoxification during both gametophytic and embryogenic development rather than driving
440 stage-specific transitions.

441 Together, these patterns support a framework in which ASC-dependent redox buffering
442 primarily supports microspore and pollen survival in both cultivars, whereas efficient GSH
443 recycling becomes especially important in rapidly dividing, embryogenic cells of Igri.
444 Supporting this view, a recent report showed that a local GSH burst in wounded Arabidopsis
445 roots shortens G1 to accelerate division and regeneration (Lee et al., 2025), offering a plausible
446 mechanistic link. Consistently, exogenous GSH in our earlier works maintained microspore
447 viability and stimulated ELS development (Žur et al., 2019; 2021b).

448
449 *Cumulative activity of thiol reductases as underestimated element of successful microspore*
450 *reprogramming*

451 Thiol oxidoreductases further integrate redox control with development. *TRXs* and
452 *GRXs*—abundant and broadly localized—regulate protein redox state, reduce disulphide and
453 mixed disulphide bonds using ferredoxin/NADPH (*TRX* systems) or GSH (*GRX*), and can
454 donate electrons to other antioxidant enzymes (Meyer et al., 2009; 2012; Sevilla et al., 2023).
455 They also participate in retrograde communication that coordinates gene expression during
456 stress acclimation (Sevilla et al., 2023). We observed selective late (stages II–III) induction of
457 specific *TRX* and *GRX* members, particularly in Igri, consistent with roles in supporting rapid
458 divisions and stabilizing redox-sensitive enzymes during multicellular structures formation.
459 Notably, this cultivar-biased late activation was independently supported by comparison with
460 the ME-responsive cultivar Gobernadora, in which several of the same thiol–redox genes were
461 previously reported as upregulated during late induction (Bélanger et al., 2018), providing
462 cross-study validation of the observed patterns. Among *PRXs*, only one gene
463 (HORVU.MOREX.r2.3HG0231680.1; a B-type/1-Cys peroxiredoxin orthologue of
464 Arabidopsis) showed a clear association with efficient ME, being strongly induced at stage III
465 in Igri and reaching high abundance (>200 FPKM). Plant 1-Cys *PRXs*, though less
466 characterized, interact with *TRX/GRX* systems to mitigate ROS, transduce stress signals, and
467 modulate metabolism, under severe stress their peroxidase activity can switch to a chaperone
468 function (Dietz et al., 2006; Kim et al., 2011; Liebthal et al., 2018). Its strong induction in the
469 responsive cultivar points to a role in proteostasis during rapid proliferative remodeling.

470 In addition to ME-associated induction, a substantial subset of *TRX/GRX/PRX* genes
471 was strongly expressed in mature pollen but showed little or no responsiveness during ME
472 induction, indicating that thiol–redox regulation also supports late gametophytic development
473 independently of embryogenic reprogramming. This separation of expression patterns suggests
474 functional specialization within thiol–redox families, with distinct members contributing either
475 to pollen maturation and stress tolerance or to the redox remodeling required for embryogenic
476 transition.

477
478 *Confirmation of the important role of GST in ME induction*

479 *GSTs* likely contribute to ME through multiple mechanisms. They catalyzing S-
480 glutathionylation—a reversible modification that shields protein thiols from irreversible
481 oxidation while modulating protein function (Sevilla et al., 2023). *GSTs* detoxify stress-derived
482 metabolites and participate in biosynthetic pathways (Piślewska-Bednarek et al., 2018).
483 Although some plant *GSTs* show limited glutathionylating activity (Micic et al., 2024), the
484 family’s size underscores functional breadth. In the present study, *GST* transcription was
485 progressively activated during ME induction, with a pronounced enrichment at stage III in the
486 responsive cultivar Igri. This pattern closely parallels observations made in the independently
487 characterised ME-responsive cultivar Gobernadora (Bélanger et al., 2018), in which late-stage
488 *GSTs* induction was likewise associated with successful embryogenic development. The

489 concordant late *GST* activation in both Igrí and Gobernadora therefore confirms their shared
490 responsive phenotype and provides cross-study validation that stage-III *GST* upregulation is a
491 hallmark of effective embryogenic reprogramming.

492 Early studies identified *GSTs* among the first ME-responsive genes in barley (Vrinten
493 et al., 1999), and subsequent studies documented dynamic *GST* expression across induction and
494 its association with plant regeneration capacity (Maraschin et al., 2006; Muñoz-Amatriaín et
495 al., 2006; Muñoz-Amatriaín et al., 2009; Joosen et al., 2007; Malik et al., 2007; Tsuwamoto
496 et al., 2007; Jacquard et al., 2009; Sánchez-Díaz et al., 2013; Žur et al., 2014b; Bélanger et al.,
497 2020). Our findings extend these observations by resolving stage- and cultivar-specific
498 programs and implicating elevated *GST* activity as a hallmark of the responsive trajectory.

499 *A Model for Redox Control during ME*

500 Integrating transcript abundance patterns across antioxidant and redox gene families
501 with their functional relationships (Fig. 6), we propose a staged model of redox control during
502 ME. An early phase, common to both cultivars, is characterized by activation of core
503 antioxidant defenses that buffer the oxidative burst associated with microspore isolation and
504 osmotic/starvation stress, thereby enabling cell survival and entry into developmental
505 reprogramming. This phase is marked by stable or moderately elevated expression of *SODs*,
506 *APXs*, and selected *CAT* and *GPX* isoforms, consistent with maintenance of basal ROS
507 detoxification and redox homeostasis.

508 In contrast, the embryogenically responsive trajectory represented by Igrí shows a
509 second, coordinated redox reinforcement at later stages (II–III), coincident with the initiation
510 of the embryogenic developmental program. This late phase involves enhanced glutathione
511 recycling via GR, pronounced activation of *GSTs*, and selective deployment of thiol–redox
512 regulators (*TRXs*, *GRXs*, and *PRXs*), rather than a global increase in antioxidant capacity
513 (highlighted in Fig. 6). Such targeted engagement of thiol-based redox hubs is well suited to
514 fine-tune protein redox status, preserve proteostasis, and sustain redox-sensitive signaling
515 pathways during rapid cell proliferation and multicellular structure formation. We propose that
516 this program maintains a signaling-competent $O_2^{\cdot-}$ and H_2O_2 pools while preventing oxidative
517 damage, thereby favoring cell-cycle progression and ELS development. Intensive utilization of
518 GSH as an electron donor by GST, GRX, and GPX enzymes may shift the cellular redox
519 balance toward a more oxidized state conducive to continued embryogenic development
520 (Stasolla, 2010). By contrast, the recalcitrant cultivar Golden Promise may over-scavenge or
521 mistime key steps, attenuating ROS signaling required for the fate switch.

522 The presented model appears to be supported by multiple experimental data (as
523 referenced above); however, further validation could be achieved via (i) targeted perturbation
524 of candidate nodes (e.g. *CAT*/*GPX* inhibition or *GSH* supplementation), (ii) real-time
525 compartment-specific redox imaging (e.g. roGFP-based reporters), and (iii) genetic
526 manipulation of discriminative *TRX/GRX/PRX* and *GST* candidates.

527 **Conclusions**

528 Our *in silico* analysis shows that transcription of antioxidant and redox genes is dynamically
529 remodeled during ME induction in barley, underscoring the centrality of redox homeostasis in
530 successful microspore reprogramming. We delineate, for the first time, the breadth and stage-
531 resolved coordination of this regulatory network in response to ME-associated stress and
532 highlight candidate contributors—including *MDHAR*, *GR*, specific *TRX/GRX* and *PRX*
533 members, and multiple *GSTs* (Fig.6). Contrasting responsiveness between cultivars enabled the
534 nomination of candidate molecular markers potentially linked to embryogenic competence.
535 These findings provide mechanistic insight into ME and offer practical leads for improving DH
536 production in cereals.

Usunięto: A, B

Usunięto: (Fig. 6A)

Usunięto: (Fig. 6B)

Usunięto: ¶

543

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708 Declaration of competing interest

709 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
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715 Authorship contribution statement

716 **Anna Nowicka:** Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Zbyněk Milec:** Data
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731 **Supplementary Information**

732 **Dataset S1.** Expression data for all antioxidant-annotated genes in barley.

733 **Figure S1.** Phenotypic progression of barley microspores during induction of microspore
734 embryogenesis.

735 **Figure S2.** Expression profiles of core antioxidant enzyme gene families.

736 **Figure S3.** Expression profiles of ascorbate–glutathione cycle gene families.

737 **Figure S4.** Expression profiles of thiol–redox regulatory genes.

738 **Figure S5.** Expression profiles of *GST* genes.

739 **Data availability**

740 RNA sequencing data were deposited at the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO;
741 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/>): GSE233486. All other relevant data can be found within
742 the manuscript and its supporting materials.

743 **Figure description**

744 **Figure 1. Antioxidant network and sampling stages during microspore embryogenesis.**

745 (A) Schematic of the ROS-scavenging network surveyed in this study. Core antioxidants:
746 SUPEROXIDE DISMUTASE (SOD), CATALASE (CAT) and GLUTATHIONE
747 PEROXIDASE (GPX). Ascorbate–glutathione (ASC–GSH) cycle: ASCORBATE
748 PEROXIDASE (APX), MONODEHYDROASCORBATE REDUCTASE (MDHAR) and
749 GLUTATHIONE REDUCTASE (GR). Thiol–redox regulators: THIOREDOXIN (TRX),
750 GLUTAREDOXIN (GRX), and PEROXIREDOXIN (PRX). S-glutathionylation is mediated
751 by GLUTATHIONE S-TRANSFERASE (GST).

752 (B) Gene families and numbers of annotated barley genes (HORVU.MOREX.r2).
753 (C) Cytological composition across ME induction stages in two cultivars, Golden Promise (GP;
754 recalcitrant) and Igri (responsive). Stage 0: microspores/bicellulars isolated from freshly
755 harvested spikes. Stage I: isolates from anthers pre-treated 48 h in 0.4 M mannitol (21 °C).
756 Stage II: isolates after mannitol-pretreatment followed by 24 h culture in KBP medium. Stage
757 III: isolates after mannitol-pretreatment followed by 48 h in KBP. Icons with percentage bars
758 indicate the proportions of uninucleate microspores, bicellular structures (after symmetric
759 division) and multicellular structures (continued symmetric divisions). Detailed percentages
760 and additional phenotypes are shown in **Fig. S1**. Quantitative data redrawn from (Nowicka et
761 al., 2024).

762 **Figure 2. Transcriptional dynamics of genes encoding core antioxidant enzymes during
763 early microspore embryogenesis in barley.**

764 (A) Heatmaps showing stage- and cultivar-specific expression patterns of representative
765 *SUPEROXIDE DISMUTASE* (*SOD*; n = 10 of 15 transcriptionally active), *CATALASE* (*CAs*; n
766 = 4 of 9 transcriptionally active), and *GLUTATHIONE PEROXIDASE* (*GPX*; n = 4 of 5
767

771 transcriptionally active) genes in Golden Promise (GP) and Igri. Expression values are shown
772 as row-wise Z-scores; the top row in each block represents the mean expression of all detected
773 members of the corresponding gene family. Only genes with detectable expression (FPKM >
774 0) in at least one stage in either cultivar were included. Stages 0–III represent successive steps
775 of ME induction, whereas P denotes bicellular pollen (gametophytic development). Gene
776 identifiers are abbreviated by omitting the common HORVU.MOREX.r2 prefix. ▲ indicates
777 genes plotted in panel (B); bold gene IDs denote genes discussed in the text. ★ indicates marker
778 genes, defined as transcripts exhibiting stage-specific and/or cultivar-specific expression during
779 ME induction.

780 (B) Expression trajectories for selected *SOD*, *CAT* and *GPX* genes across ME stages. Asterisks
781 indicate between-cultivar differences at a given stage (DESeq2, FDR-adjusted $P < 0.05$); 'ns'
782 indicates non-significance. Background shading indicates genes classified as stage-specific
783 (grey), Igri-specific (green), or Golden Promise-specific (yellow). Dashed horizontal lines
784 indicate the corresponding pollen expression level for each cultivar. Additional information on
785 these gene families is provided in Fig. S2.

786

787 **Figure 3. Transcriptional dynamics of ascorbate–glutathione (ASC–GSH) cycle genes**
788 **during early microspore embryogenesis in barley.**

789 (A) Heatmaps of representative *ASCORBATE PEROXIDASE* (*APX*; n = 2 out of 4
790 transcriptionally active), *MONODEHYDROASCORBATE REDUCTASE* (*MDHAR*; n = 5, all
791 transcriptionally active) and *GLUTATHIONE REDUCTASE* (*GR*; n=2, all transcriptionally
792 active) genes showing stage- and cultivar-specific expression patterns (row Z-scores) in Golden
793 Promise (GP) and Igri. The top row in each block indicates the mean expression of all detected
794 members of the corresponding gene family. Only genes with detectable expression (FPKM >
795 0) in at least one stage in either cultivar were included. Stages 0–III represent successive steps
796 of ME induction, whereas P denotes bicellular pollen (gametophytic development). Gene IDs
797 are abbreviated by omitting the common HORVU.MOREX.r2 prefix. ▲ indicates genes plotted
798 in panel (B); bold gene IDs denote genes discussed in the text. ★ indicates marker genes,
799 defined as transcripts exhibiting stage-specific and/or cultivar-specific expression during ME
800 induction.

801 (B) Expression trajectories for selected *APX*, *MDHAR* and *GR* genes across ME stages.
802 Asterisks indicate between-cultivar differences at a given stage (DESeq2, FDR-adjusted
803 $P < 0.05$); 'ns' indicates non-significance. Background shading indicates genes classified as
804 stage-specific (grey), Igri-enriched (green) or Golden Promise-enriched (yellow). Dashed
805 horizontal lines indicate the corresponding pollen expression level for each cultivar. Additional
806 family-level expression summaries are provided in Fig. S3.

807

808 **Figure 4. Transcriptional dynamics of thiol–redox regulatory genes during early**
809 **microspore embryogenesis in barley.**

810 (A) Heatmaps of representative *THIOREDOXIN* (*TRX*; n = 14 out of 57 transcriptionally
811 active), *GLUTAREDOXIN* (*GRX*; n = 12 out of 37 transcriptionally active) and
812 *PEROXIREDOXIN* (*PRX*; n = 4 out of 8 transcriptionally active) genes showing stage- and
813 cultivar-specific expression patterns (row Z-scores) in Golden Promise (GP) and Igri. The top
814 row in each block indicates the mean expression of all detected members of the corresponding
815 gene family. Only genes with detectable expression (FPKM > 0) in at least one stage in either
816 cultivar were included. Stages 0–III represent successive steps of ME induction, whereas P
817 denotes bicellular pollen (gametophytic development). Symbols next to gene IDs denote: bold
818 gene IDs genes discussed in the text. ★ indicates marker genes, defined as transcripts exhibiting
819 stage-specific and/or cultivar-specific expression during ME induction. ▲ indicates genes
820 plotted in panel (B). ■ marks genes reported as upregulated at day 5 of culture in the ME-

821 responsive cultivar Gobernadora (Bélanger et al., 2018). Detailed data are provided in Dataset
822 1.

823 (B) Expression trajectories for selected *TRX*, *GRX*, and *PRX* genes across ME stages. Asterisks
824 indicate between-cultivar differences at a given stage (DESeq2, FDR-adjusted $P < 0.05$); 'ns'
825 indicates non-significance. Shading indicates the stage where each gene is stage-specific (grey),
826 Igri-specific (green), or Golden Promise-specific (yellow). Dashed horizontal lines indicate the
827 pollen expression level for each cultivar. Additional family-level expression summaries for
828 *TRXs/GRXs/PRXs* and *THIOREDOXIN REDUCTASEs (TRXR)s* are provided in **Fig. S4**.

829
830 **Figure 5. Transcriptional dynamics of *GLUTATHIONE S-TRANSFERASE (GST)* genes
831 during early microspore embryogenesis in barley.**

832 (A) Heatmap of 34 representative *GST* genes (out of 180 transcriptionally active) showing
833 stage- and cultivar-dependent expression patterns in Golden Promise (GP) and Igri. Expression
834 is displayed as row Z-scores; the top row indicates the mean expression of all detected *GSTs*.
835 Only genes with detectable expression (FPKM > 0) in at least one stage in either cultivar were
836 included. Stages 0–III represent successive steps of ME induction, whereas P denotes bicellular
837 pollen (gametophytic development). Gene IDs are abbreviated by omitting the common
838 HORVU.MOREX.r2 prefix. Symbols next to gene IDs denote: ▲ genes plotted in panel (B);
839 ● *GSTs* reported as upregulated in the ME-responsive cultivar Gobernadora at days 0–2 of
840 culture; ■ *GSTs* reported as upregulated in Gobernadora at day 5 (Bélanger et al., 2018).
841 indicates marker genes, defined as transcripts exhibiting stage-specific and/or cultivar-specific
842 expression during ME induction. Bold gene IDs indicate genes specifically discussed in the
843 main text. Extended data are provided in Dataset 1 and in Fig. S5.

844 (B) Expression trajectories (FPKM) for selected *GSTs* across ME stages in GP and Igri.
845 Asterisks indicate significant between-cultivar differences at a given stage (DESeq2; FDR-
846 adjusted $P < 0.05$); ns denotes non-significance. Background shading indicates genes classified
847 as stage-specific (grey) or Igri-enriched (green). Dashed horizontal lines indicate the
848 corresponding pollen expression level for each cultivar. Additional family-level expression
849 summaries are provided in **Fig. S5**.

850
851 **Figure 6. Conceptual model summarizing transcriptome-derived redox regulatory dynamics**
852 **underlying barley microspore embryogenesis induction.**

853 Short-term osmotic stress (1-2 h of 0.4 M mannitol) applied during anthers collection together with the
854 stress induced by mechanical isolation of microspores (Stage 0) triggers reactive oxygen species (ROS)
855 production and redox signaling, leading to activation of core antioxidant defenses and initiation of
856 microspore reprogramming. This early phase is characterized by elevated expression of *SUPEROXIDE*
857 *DISMUTASES (SODs)* and *ASCORBATE PEROXIDASES (APXs)*, together with induction of thiol-
858 based redox regulators, including *THIOREDOXINS (TRXs)* and *PEROXIREDOXINS (PRXs)*. Prolonged
859 osmotic/starvation stress (Stage I) sustains ROS signaling and reinforces coordinated antioxidant
860 responses, supporting commitment to and stabilization of the reprogramming process. Following
861 transfer to nutrient medium (Stages II–III), a broader redox network becomes established, incorporating
862 *CATALASES (CATs)*, *GLUTATHIONE PEROXIDASES (GPXs)*, *MONODEHYDROASCORBATE*
863 *REDUCTASES (MDHARs)*, *GLUTATHIONE REDUCTASES (GRs)*, *GLUTAREDOXINS (GRXs)*,
864 *TRXs*, *PRXs*, and *GLUTATHIONE S-TRANSFERASES (GSTs)*. This expanded network supports protein
865 protection, redox homeostasis, cellular restructuring, and initiation and progression of embryogenesis.
866 These redox regulatory processes represent a core transcriptional framework shared by both cultivars
867 (Igri and Golden Promise) and are essential for microspore survival and developmental reprogramming.

868 Comparative transcriptomic analysis further reveals cultivar-specific quantitative differences: the
869 responsive cultivar Igri displays higher cumulative transcript abundance of multiple antioxidant and
870 detoxification gene families, including stronger late-stage induction of GRs, enhanced activation of
871 thiol-based redox components (TRXs/GRXs/PRXs), and a more pronounced GST-mediated
872 detoxification response (highlighted in bold). Intensive utilization of GSH may shift the cellular redox
873 balance toward a more oxidized state conducive to continued embryogenic development likely
874 underpins successful embryogenesis in Igri.
875 Enzyme family names denote transcriptional regulation inferred from RNA-seq analyses and do not
876 represent direct measurements of enzymatic activity.

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Usunięto: Figure 6. Summary of antioxidant and redox gene-family dynamics during early microspore embryogenesis in barley.¶

(A) Schematic overview of cumulative transcript abundance for antioxidant and redox gene families across stages 0–III of ME induction. The upper panel shows responses that are comparable between cultivars (Igri = Golden Promise) likely important for microspore survival and reprogramming, including high, stable expression of *SUPEROXIDE DISMUTASEs (SODs)* and *ASCORBATE PEROXIDASEs (APXs)* and stage-specific upregulation of *THIOREDOXINs/ PEROXIREDOXINs (TRXs/PRXs)* induced by oxidative stress associated with microspore isolation with further up-regulation of *CATALASEs (CATs)*, *GLUTATHIONE PEROXIDASEs (GPXs)*, *MONODEHYDROASCORBATE REDUCTASEs (MDHARs)*, *THIOREDOXINs/ GLUTAREDOXINs (TRXs/GRXs)* and *GLUTATHIONE S-TRANSFERASEs (GSTs)* associated with developmental reprogramming and ME induction. ¶

The lower panel highlights families with higher cumulative abundance in Igri (Igri > Golden Promise), consistent with more effective reprogramming. Besides higher expression of *SODs*, the responsive cultivar Igri was characterized by stronger late-stage upregulation of *GLUTATHIONE REDUCTASEs (GRs)* and thiol–redox components—*TRXs/GRXs/PRXs* together with a more pronounced *GST*-mediated detoxification response. ¶

Boxes below indicate the dominant physiological context of each stage. ¶

(B) Functional integration of antioxidant systems during ME, illustrating representative biochemical reactions catalyzed by the corresponding antioxidant and redox enzymes encoded by the gene families shown in (A). These include enzymatic pathways involved in ROS detoxification (*SOD*, *CAT*, *GPX*, *APX* and *PRX*), ascorbate regeneration (*MDHAR*), glutathione recycling (*GR*), and protein redox buffering/thiol protection (*TRX*, *GRX* and *GST*).

Figure 1.JPEG

Figure 2.JPEG

Figure 3.JPEG

Figure 4.JPEG

A

Figure 5.JPEG

Cumulative transcript abundance of antioxidant and redox gene families across early ME stages

B

Functional integration of antioxidant systems during ME

Figure 6.JPEG

